

WHO OR WHAT COULD HELP TO PREVENT CORRUPTION IN UZBEKISTAN?

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to state that corruption is the main problem that hampers socio-economic development globally. To nip unethical behavior in the bud everyone has a role, especially mothers whose position is by far the most influential among others. Or, is there any mechanism to find a solution for the elimination of this endemic corruption?*

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Societies' developments in all spheres depend on overcoming difficulties which might face all level of people from blue collar workers to white collar workers. To have sustainable development all the obstacles should be allocated equally and aptly between people. For, there is no one single problem that cannot be tackled. Giving a helping hand to each other problems are easy to solve totally, and certainly societies are able to cut many global catastrophic issues.

However, several problems are emerging due to not understanding the root of these problems. Even it is sometimes enough difficult how to address some matters or charge somebody with investigating any problems which are being the threats to promote sustainable development.

One of the main problems that hamper socio-economic development globally is corruption. To nip unethical behavior in the bud everyone has a role, especially mothers whose position is by far the most influential among others. Or, is there any mechanism to find a solution for the elimination of this endemic corruption?

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development establishes the equality between genders as well as women empower as a best achievement, and regarded all types of corruption is one of its goals. In order for its Members to aid attaining the Sustainable Development Goals, the Women Development Organization is putting forward to advance the subject overall comprehending network of corruption and women role taking part in combating corruption which is one among other four pillars forming its first program cycle. WDO concludes that the power or the way which improve anti-corruption and gender equality is to promote literacy.

Several surveys conducted by Lambsdorff and Frank (2011), Sockemer et al. (2020), Wangnerund and Sundell (2012), Alexander and Ravlik (2015), Bauhr et al. (2019) found that women in power can reduce corruption through overseeing fairly and strictly. They assume women empowerment in government could assist to prevent corrupt behavior and remove the barriers of social services that make ways for social mobility as well as lessens gender inequalities.

Despite of the facts given above, women engagement in power does not mean that they are as panaceas for corruption. Still, any kinds of corruption gradually reduce people's trust and the quality of countries' governmental services.

An abundance of measures and laws have been implemented to fight against corruption worldwide as well in Uzbekistan. Even being aware of the negative consequences of corruption, it can be quite difficult for many people to resist it. Psychologically, some people are eager to live in the lap of luxury, thus they prioritize their own matters first behind others. Moreover, some wish to gain more monetary benefit no matter how, some have a personality trait to receive gifts, and some want to have easy solutions to their problems, but some have fear to be fired from their jobs. These are all typical examples of behaving behind ethical norms or just flourishing corrupt practices.

The most correct mechanism that really works well would definitely be mothers' nurture, the school system and of course the school administration. If the arrangement between the three can work systematically, living standards will be improved. These three play a major role through combating corruption in many ways and pave the way for development of societies.

Considering corruption is as all the restrictions of development and the education is the key element of preventing it, much effort and attention have been given to education in Uzbekistan. Interestingly, the majority of teachers who are conducting their professional jobs are females. The percentage of female school principles is also more than comparing male ones. Aiding to enhance the quality of lessons, there is no exact survey about whether male or female teachers lead their lessons productively. Furthermore, it is still unknown which gender teachers are tend to do malpractices like nepotism, favoritism, clientelism and patronage while fulfilling their duties in Uzbekistan.

Thus, it was so honorable to have been given more respect and attention for women and girls who were too eager to continue their master's degree. Gaining admission for further studying fairly women got an admirable opportunity to not paying any tuition fees in this academic year in Uzbekistan. So many reasons might be stated towards women contribution to the development of countries to definite; however, women's role as mothers is of paramount importance to societies' development. To mention which is absolutely true is that educated mothers have clear visions about the world so that kids can distinguish what is right and what is wrong. Children's intolerance towards different unethical behavior or being engaged in corrupt practices is evolved over the years through making desperate attempts by mothers who have infinite patience to nurture. Mothers are the first corrupt prevention officers. Current status quo of the country pushes mothers to educate their offspring according to the current existing social norms and values so that they can live without suffering in life. This indicates that there is the need to eliminate any barriers and dealing with injustice which makes women more vulnerable to

resist corruption. Indeed, mothers are the most powerful educators who inculcate anti-corruption behavior to their children.

Bauhr et al (2019) has stated that more women who involved in political institutions prone to maximize the amelioration of the public services especially the fields where women get benefits i.e. in education and health areas.

It is believed that children are the future of the world as well as they become the leaders of societies. Individual character, attitude, behavior are formed firstly at home and then in schools. Thus, the mandatory educational state program serves as a second mechanism to acquire knowledge about how to resist and react strongly against corruption. So as the mechanism of anti-corruption work properly parents should interface with school teachers.

To reduce excessive bureaucracy the digital educational platform which comprises secondary school teachers, schoolchildren as well as their parents called “kunalik.com” has been installed in Uzbekistan and it has successfully started working since April 2019. The platform gives this group of people an opportunity to express their ideas, and provides interactive educational materials only for schoolchildren to broaden their knowledge.

The creation of online community via the internet can help increase double awareness about corruption when implements virtual anti-corruption educational directives and instructions to encourage the participation in the combating anti-corruption process.

The great mutual connection between parents and schools has already been set via this platform and both can send any information about corrupt practices through it anytime. This platform might be successful in cultivating more trusting and fair attitude to the educational system, of course when school administration work transparently. Hence, the disclosures about unethical behavior or corrupt practices virtually prevent and stifle this community from doing and being participants of them. In addition, this increases respect and total obedience to the educational rules and laws, and ensures equality between male and female teachers as well as identifies which gender teachers allow corruption to grow. The causes of proliferating corruption are little public awareness and involvement, participation, low contribution of civil society, lack of responsibility of public schools, social unwillingness, the status-quo, cultural mentality of society and others.

Overall, to stop and prevent corruption a proper mutual systematic mechanism should be put into practice and then strengthened.

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